

The use of plants extracts in the improvement of cowpea yield at dang (Ngaoundere, Cameroon)

Kapeuhag Latchikou Casimir^{1*}, Barry Borkeum Raoul², Wini Goudoungou Jean³, Dabolé Massah Odette¹, Ngakou Albert¹, Nukenine Elias Nchiwan¹

¹Department of Biological Sciences, Faculty of Science, University of Ngaoundere, Cameroon

²Department of Life Sciences, High Teacher Training College of Bertoua, University of Ngaoundere, Cameroon

³Department of Biological Sciences, Faculty of Science, University of Bamenda, Cameroon

Article published on January 30, 2021

Key words: *Callistemon rigidus*, *Plectranthus glandulosus*, *Lippia multiflora*, *Vigna unguiculata*, Yield

Abstract

In the substitution of chemical insecticides with potential biopesticides, the efficiency of *Lippia multiflora*, *Plectranthus glandulosus* and *Callistemon rigidus* were evaluated on the improvement of cowpea (*Vigna unguiculata*) in Dang (Ngaoundere, Cameroon). The experiment was conducted in a completely randomized block design with 5 treatments repeated 4 times each: the negative control, the positive control (Decis), *L. multiflora*, *P. glandulosus* and *C. rigidus*. These different insecticides were sprayed on cowpea plants with 14 days interval starting from the 14th day after sowing. The parameters collected were the diversity of insect pests, the number of pods, and the dry weight of the grains. All of the insecticides used improved cowpea yields. Although less efficient than Decis, most biopesticides significantly ($p < 0.001$) improved the yield of cowpeas compared to the negative control. This improvement was 260% for *C. rigidus*, and 120% for *P. glandulosus*. These results suggest that *C. rigidus*, *P. glandulosus* and *L. multiflora* could be considered as potential substitutes for chemical insecticides in improving cowpea yields.

*Corresponding Author: Kapeuhag Latchikou Casimir ✉ raoulbarry@yahoo.fr

Introduction

Agriculture in sub-Saharan Africa is essential to reduce poverty and strengthen food security (FAO, 2009a). *Vigna unguiculata* which occupies an important place in the Sudano-Sahelian and Guinean zones (Isubikalu *et al.*, 2000) would therefore be a major asset, not only for food balance, but also for economic development (Adeoti *et al.*, 2002). Indeed, this leguminous plant is cultivated for its richness in food proteins (20-25%) (Bressani, 1985; Rivas-Vega *et al.*, 2006), but its production is rather low (MINADER, 2012).

More than 80% of this low production is due to insect pests (Tamò *et al.*, 1993), and the use of chemical pesticides has often caused more problems than it has solved (Bambara and Tiemtoré, 2008). In the development of healthier control strategies to increase the productivity of cowpea, plants extracts or botanicals could be used to substitute chemical insecticides (Barry *et al.*, 2017).

This is the case of *Lippia multiflora*, which efficiency has been demonstrated on *Sitophilus zeamais* (Nukenine *et al.*, 2007), *Callistemon rigidus* which has been found to be efficient against *Aedes aegypti* and *Anopheles gambiae* larvae (Danga *et al.*, 2014b), as well as *Plectranthus glandulosus* which has been shown to be efficient against *Sitophilus oryzae*, *Sitophilus zeamais* and *Prostephanus truncatus* (Ngamo *et al.*, 2007a; Nukenine *et al.*, 20010a).

Therefore, the aim of this work was to further research on other plants (*Lippia multiflora*, *Plectranthus glandulosus* and *Callistemon rigidus*), which extracts could be of potential use as biopesticides against cowpea pests, so as to improve the yield.

Material and methods

Study site

The experiment was carried out from August to November 2017 at Dang (Ngaoundere, Cameroon). The cowpea seeds used in this work were of the BR1 variety obtained from IRAD (Research Institute for Agriculture and Development) in Maroua.

Experimental layout

The field was conducted on a 494 m² flat surface in a completely randomized blocks design comprising 5 treatments repeated 4 times each. The experimental plots separated by 1m were (4×3.5)m². The five treatments were the negative control, the aqueous extract of *Lippia multiflora* leaves, the aqueous extract of *Plectranthus glandulosus* leaves, the aqueous extract of *Callistemon rigidus* leaves, and the positive control (Decis or Deltamethrin). Plant extracts were sprayed using 4 different manual sprayers (marques), each corresponding to an insecticide treatment. These different insecticides were applied every two weeks after sowing until harvest.

Formulation of insecticides

The aqueous extracts were obtained according to Srekanth's method (2013). A total of 125g leaves from each plants used was weighed, pounded in a mortar and macerated in 1.25L tape water for 12 hours. After maceration, the mixture was filtered using a 0.2mm pore size sieve before each filtrate was introduced into the corresponding sprayer. The synthetic insecticide Decis was formulated, following the instructions of the manufacturer by diluting 3mL of Decis in 15L of tape water.

Assessment of devastating pests and yield parameters

Data collection started 3 weeks after sowing, and repeated every 10 days. The parameters measured were the number and the diversity of insect pests, the number of pods per foot and the grain yield. A lens was required to identify tiny insect pests (such as *Aphis cracivora* and *Megalurothrips sjostedti*). The number of pods per plant was counted according to the phenology of the plant. Concerning the yield, the dry weight of the seeds (inkg) was evaluated per plot.

Statistical analyses

Data were analyzed using SAS 2003 software. Data were transformed into a square root for the insect pest population, and logarithm for the number of pods and the dry weight of grains. This was to reduce variance errors. All these parameters were subjected to the analysis of variance (ANOVA) and the graphs were produced with the Excel spreadsheet of Office 2010 software.

Results

Diversity and density of insect pests on *Vigna unguiculata* plants. Several insect pests were counted in the experimental field and *Clavigralla tomentosicollis*, *Aphis craccivora*, *Megalurothrips sjostedti* and *Maruca vitrata* were respectively the most numerous (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Number of insect pest species.

Effect of treatments on pod production

The influence of the treatments on the production of pods is shown in fig. 2. It is observed that, all the biopesticides have significantly ($p < 0.001$) improved the production of pods compared to the negative control. However, Décis has been the most efficient insecticide.

Fig. 2. Variation mean of cowpea pods per plants between treatments.

Bars affected with the same letters are not different at 5% level of significantly.

Effect of treatments on grain yield (kg / ha)

The insecticide treatments significantly ($p < 0.001$) improved the cowpea yield compared to the negative control, except for *L. multiflora*. These results are shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Variation cowpea yield (kg/ha) between treatments.

Bars affected with the same letters are not different at 5% level of significantly.

Discussion

In the improvement of cowpea yield by using biopesticides as substitutes for chemical insecticides, the treatments used in this work had an influence on the parameters measured.

With regard to the density and diversity of cowpea insect pests, the high number of *A. craccivora*, *M. sjostedti*, *M. vitrata* and *M. tomentosicollis* highlights the consideration of these insects as major pests of cowpea (Mehinto *et al.*, 2014). *A. craccivora* by attacking the young plant and the soft parts of the plant (Dougje, 2009), severely reduces the development of cowpeas. *M. sjostedti*, which causes necrosis of flower buds and flowers (Dougje, 2009), destroys the reproductive organs of cowpeas, with consequence that the plant can no longer produce fruits (Barry, 2018). As for *M. vitrata* and *M. tomentosicollis*, they drill and dry the pods (Dougje, 2009). Attacks on cowpea by these insects pest therefore contribute to considerable yield losses.

In pod production, the major efficiency of Décis compared to that of biopesticides would be due to its broad spectrum of action and the fact that it is systemic (Barry *et al.*, 2017). The reduced efficiency of *L. multiflora* and *P. glandulosus* when compared to that of *C. rigidus* is due to their volatility. This would explain their high efficiency in storage rather than in the field, which is not a confined place. These results are similar to those of Barry *et al.*, 2019 and those of Bambara and Tiemtoré (2008) who showed the reduced efficiency of neem in the field.

The properties of *P. glandulosus* (Ngamo *et al.*, 2007a; Nukenine *et al.*, 20010a) and *C. rigidus* (Danga *et al.*, 2014b) have enabled them to improve cowpea yield, and even to equal the efficiency of the Decis with regard to *C. rigidus*. Indeed, the efficiency of *P. glandulosus* higher than that of *L. multiflora* could show the higher volatility of the latter, thus highlighting the importance of adhesion in the efficiency of insecticides (Ibrahim *et al.*, 1999). These results are similar to those of Barry (2018). The terpenoids, flavonoids, steroids and saponins (Praveen *et al.*, 2012) contained in *C. rigidus*, give it its insecticidal activities. *C. rigidus* therefore fought the insect pests responsible for cowpea yield losses as effectively as the Decis.

Conclusion

This work is a contribution to the improvement of cowpea yield through the use of biopesticides. It appears that the treatments used in this work as potential substitutes for chemical insecticides, *P. glandulosus* and *C. rigidus* have proven to be effective in improving cowpea yield. Much more, *C. rigidus* was as effective as the Decis. However, we have to seek the improvement of the efficiency of less effective treatments.

References

Adéoti R, Coulibaly O, Tamò M. 2002. Facteurs affectant l'adoption des nouvelles technologies du niébé *Vigna unguiculata* en Afrique de l'Ouest. Bulletin de la Recherche Agronomique du Bénin **36**, 18p.

Bambara D, Tiemtoré J. 2008. Efficacité biopesticide de *Hyptis spicigera* Lam., *Azadirachta indica* A. Juss. et *Euphorbia balsamifera* Ait. sur le niébé *Vigna unguiculata* L. Walp. Tropicultura **26**, 53-55.

Barry BR, Ngakou A, Nukenine EN. 2017. Pesticidal Activity of Plant Extracts and a Mycoinsecticide (*Metarhizium anisopliae*) on Cowpea flower Thrips and Leaves Damages in the Field. Journal of Experimental Agriculture International **18(2)**, 1-15, 2017.

Barry BR, Ngakou A, Tamò M, Nukenine EN. 2019. The incidence of aqueous neem leaves (*Azadirachta indica* A. Juss) extract and *Metarhizium anisopliae* Metch. on cowpea thrips (*Megolurothrips sjostedti* Trybom) and yield in Ngaoundéré (Adamaoua, Cameroun). Journal of Entomology and Zoology Studies **7(5)**, 333-338.

Barry BR. 2018. Impact d'extraits de plantes et d'un mycoinsecticide sur la population de thrips et le rendement du niébé à Ngaoundéré et à Maroua (Cameroun). Thèse de Doctorat/PhD, Université de Ngaoundéré 155p.

Bressani R. 1985. Nutritive value of cowpea. In: Cowpea Research, Production and Utilization. Singh S. R., Rachel K. O. (Eds). Wiley and Sons, Chester, UK PP. 353-360.

Danga YSP, Esimone CO, Younoussa L, Nukenine EN. 2014b. Larvicidal and pupicidal activities of *Plectranthus glandulosus* and *Callistemon rigidus* leaf essential oils against three mosquito species. J. Mosq. Res **4**, 5-14.

Dugje IY, Omoigui LO, Ekeleme F, Kamara AY, Ajeigbe H. 2009. Production du niébé en Afrique de l'Ouest. Guide du Paysan IITA 26p.

Ibrahim L, Butt T, Beckett A, Clark SJ. 1999. The germination oil-formulated conidia of the insect pathogen *Metarhizium anisopliae*. Mycol. Res **103**, 901-907.

- Isubikalu P, Erbaugh JM, Semana AR, Adipala E.** 2000. The influence of farmer perception on pesticide usage for management of cowpea field pest in eastern Uganda. *Africa Crop Science Journal* **8**, 317-325.
- Mehinto JT, Atachi P, Elégbédé M, Kpindou OKD, Tamò M.** 2014. Efficacité comparée des insecticides de natures différentes dans la gestion des insectes ravageurs du niébé au Centre du Bénin. *Journal of Applied Biosciences* **84**, 7695-7706.
- Minader / Desa.** 2012. Annuaire des Statistiques du secteur Agricole, Campagnes 2009 & 2010. Direction des Enquêtes et des Statistiques Agricoles. *AGRI-STAT N° 17*, 123 p.
- Ngamo TSL, Ngassoum MB, Mapongmestsem PM, Noudjou WF.** 2007a. Use of Essential Oil of Plants as Protectant of Grains during Storage. *Agricultural Journal* **2(2)**, 204-209.
- Nukenine EN, Adler C, Reichmuth C.** 2007. Efficacy evaluation of plant powders from Cameroon as post-harvest grain protectants against the infestation of *Sitophilus zeamais* Motschulsky (Coleoptera: Curculionidae). *Journal of Plant Disease and Protection* **114(1)**, 30-36.
- Nukenine EN, Adler C, Reichmuth C.** 2010a. Bioactivity of fenchone and *Plectranthus glandulosus* oil against *Prostephanus truncatus* and two strains of *Sitophilus zeamais*. *J. Appl. Ent* **134**, 132-141.
- Praveenk, Renuka J, Shweta J, Archana S.** 2012. A Review on biological and investigation of plant genus *Callistemon*. *Asian Pac J. Trop. Biomed* (2012): S1906-S1909.
- Sreekanth.** 2013. Field evaluation of certain leaf extracts for the control of mussel scale (*Lepidosaphes piperis* Gr.) in Black pepper (*Piper nigrum* L.). *Journal of Biopesticides* **6(1)**, 1-15.
- Tamò M, Baumgärtner J, Gutierrez AP.** 1993. Analysis of cowpea monocropping system in West Africa. II. Modelling the interaction between cowpea and the bean flower thrips *Megalurothrips sjostedti* (Trybom) Thysanoptera: Thripidae. *Ecological Modelling* **70**, 89-113.